

Automatic Classification of Interactive Gestures for Inter-Body Proximity Sonification

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigates the possibility of classifying interactive gestures from one-dimensional inter-body proximity. The sensor data for training and classification have been acquired within the interdisciplinary research project *Sentire*. The project combines artistic human-computer interaction, real-world research, and sonic interaction design and investigates how body movements mediated by musical sounds promote interactive and prosocial behaviours. The closed-loop interactive system ‘Sentire’ can sonify proximity and touch between two users in real time. We describe its sonic interaction design based on one-dimensional parameter input and our approach to learning interactive gestures from the continuous sensor data stream. Our model uses two convolutional neural networks (CNNs). One CNN processes the proximity signal and its speed calculation. The second learns frame-wise features from those two signals; an objective aligns the two CNNs through a sigmoid activation layer. Despite the small data set and the low dimensionality of our sensor data, we can predict interactive behaviours that intuitively affect the proximity signal. Especially gestures with arm movements perform significantly better than a baseline classifier based on linear regression.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Italian word *sentire* [senˈtɪːre] means both to hear and to feel. *Sentire* is a digital system that mediates between bodily movements and musical sounds. Inter-body proximity and touch can be sensed and mapped to an algorithmic sound environment in real time, allowing for a closed-loop auditory interaction between two users. We map the continuous, one-dimensional output of our underlying sensor technology to a specific set of sound parameters, whereby inter-body touch is the only case for which we use a distinct parameter mapping from the continuous proximity sonification [1]. We hypothesise that adding specific interaction behaviours to the gestural input space can help to promote

prosocial behaviours (prosociality). Therefore, we investigate whether a deep learning model can predict specific interaction behaviours from the one-dimensional sensor output (proximity). The data for training and classification has been acquired within the interdisciplinary research project *Sentire*, which combines artistic human-computer interaction, real-world research, and sonic interaction design. The coding system for the annotations was developed through structured observation (SO) from two studies with *Sentire* [1], [2]. SO is an empirical method for behavioural analysis and is particularly effective for analysing complex non-verbal behaviour. Although Rizzonelli et al. [1] did not develop the codes specifically for gesture recognition, a particular subset of the coding scheme is suitable as a basis for training and evaluating the classifier. Our approach to classifying interaction gestures is distinct from similar research since: (1) the data set was gathered from auditory interactions between two users (dyadic sonic interaction); (2) the output from the sensor used for training is one-dimensional; (3) our deep learning model architecture is suitable for real-time gesture sonification. First, we present related work and the theoretical background of our research. Then, we describe the data collection, the pre-processing of the sensor data, and the model architecture. Finally, we present the metrics for the trained models and interpret the results for different interactive gestures.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Gesture and pattern recognition from motion sensor data is a topic researched across disciplines and with different aims; from the vast and debatable field of biometrics, which usually focuses on activity recognition (AR) or user recognition (UR) [3]–[9] to more human-centred applications like assisted learning [10]–[12], sonic interaction design [13]–[16] and art [17]–[19]. We distinguish the different approaches by sensor modality, dimensionality, computational method and real-time feasibility.

Vision-based systems for motion tracking usually produce a high dimensional sensor output and are linked to computational effort and real-time constraints. Whereas inertial measurement units (IMUs), which measure acceleration, orientation and angular velocity, are cheap and require less space and processing resources. Considering that each raw data modality has its limitations, hybrid solutions can

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increase recognition capabilities by combining different modalities and therefore increasing dimensionality [14]–[16], [20]. In contrast to these high-dimensional solutions, DeepEar [21] relies only on one-dimensional microphone input for real-time scene analysis, emotion recognition, stress detection and UR. DeepSense [22] is a classification framework that accommodates various applications and can combine different sensor modalities and dimensions. Visi and Tanaka [18] provide an overview of interactive machine learning techniques for analysing and designing musical gestures. Sonifying (musical) gestures does not necessarily include machine learning. It can also be based on raw sensor input or the computation of higher-level statistical features [10], [11], [23]–[25].

On the one hand, traditional machine learning approaches are still a good choice for gesture recognition, especially for real-time applications [8], [12], [14], [26]. On the other hand, deep learning is trending in current research [3]–[7], [9], [19], [22]. Recent image-based gesture recognition systems primarily build on generative adversarial networks (GANs, e.g. [19]). In contrast, systems with wearable sensors tend to use convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [3], [5], [6] or a combination of CNNs with recurrent neural networks (RNN) [7] respectively long short-term memory (LSTM) networks [4], [9]. Few research investigates gesture recognition in an interactive social context similar to Sentire [13], [27]. Other work does not implement machine learning or deep learning yet specifically focuses on interactive sonification strategies for motion [28], interaction design concerning embodiment [29], or artistic exploration of gesture sonification using a phenomenological approach [30]. To our best knowledge, our work is the first to evaluate a deep learning method for gesture recognition in the social context based only on one-dimensional sensor data (proximity) and suitable for real-time sonification.

3. SONIFYING DYADIC INTERACTION

In order to understand the sonification concepts behind sentire and our approach to sonifying dyadic interaction in general, it is essential to have an overview of the systems’ architecture and some of its core characteristics.

Figure 1 shows the signal flow of our interactive system from sensor input to auditory feedback. To obtain a control signal in the digital domain, we use our software written in SuperCollider [31]. Converting the “raw” sensor signal (48kHz) into a proximity and touch signal is part of the sensor system (i.e. the gestural input). In contrast, despite using the same software framework, the sonification stage is part of the sound generator as defined in [32]. We map the sensor system’s proximity and touch signal output to selected parameters of an algorithmic sound synthesis process to generate real-time feedback. Making this signal audible through a sound system enables closed-loop auditory interaction. We call the set of parameters that defines the tonal quality of the auditory feedback a “sound environment” (SE) [1]. A SE results from creative decisions regarding sound design, algorithmic composition and a specific parameter mapping that connects the gestural input (proximity and touch) to the sound synthesis processes

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of Sentire, including—from top to bottom—the sensor hardware (blue), the sensor data processing (orange) and sound generation (red).

(“sound sources”). In the broader context of *auditory displays*, and following the taxonomy of [33], a SE constitutes a *parameter mapping sonification*. It combines *continuous* (proximity) with *event-based* (touch) sonification, and although the input data are *quantitative* (physical proximity), a SE also implicitly maps abstract, *qualitative* aspects of interpersonal distance, such as intimacy, to sound. Creating a SE and choosing a parameter mapping strategy resembles well-established paradigms of sonic interaction design. Still, the one-dimensional character of the gestural input and the nature of dyadic sonic interaction demands specific approaches. According to [33] our sonification techniques follow the function of *monitoring* or more specifically they “promote the awareness of task-related processes”.

The task during a sentire interaction is sometimes not explicitly set or can be unknown to the interactant. However, when designing a SE we follow strategies to shape the interaction space in specific ways, and navigating this space can be seen as an implicit task during the sonic interaction. We generally aim to promote interactive behaviours and prosociality. For this purpose, we follow two key strategies: to increase *kinaesthetic perception* (see section 3.1) and to intensify *the intimate and personal space* (see section 3.3). Whereas the interaction designer and the performer or therapist are aware of these strategies, the regular Sentire user is not informed about them. Navigating both the gestural and the social space becomes an exploratory act that promotes the interaction’s broader goal.

During years of artistic, performative practice with the system [34], we established the following sonic interaction design strategies: (a) mapping amplitude to proximity so that the interaction starts with silence and reaches its maximum loudness closely before the interactants touch; (b) map-

ping one “main” parameter that distinctly changes the tonal quality and thus is easy to track (usually frequency/pitch or duration/rhythm); (c) applying a non-linear mapping to the above parameters to make the perceived change more prominent in the intimate space; (d) mapping touch to a unique sound event; and (e) alternating the tonal quality of the touch sound based on the touch duration.

3.1 Kinaesthetic Perception

Based on the research of Kim et al. [35] we presume that social interaction is entrenched in the perception and selection of one’s own and the other’s behaviour and in distinguishing the self from the other. Accordingly, we ground social interaction on kinaesthetic perception and coordination [1]. Kinaesthetic perception—the perception of one’s own movements [36] is one of the necessary conditions for coordination. We reflect these assumptions in our “one-to-many” parameter mappings, which map a one-dimensional gestural parameter (proximity) to multiple musical parameters simultaneously. With the above mapping strategies (b) and (d), we keep the action-perception cycle coherent and easy to understand, assuming this is crucial for kinaesthetic perception and explicit gestural agency.

3.2 Gestural Agency

Mendoza and Thompson define “gestural agency” as an agent’s influence over other agents within a musical ecosystem [37]. The authors abstract the various signals connecting the network of agents as “gestural space”. The low-dimensional gestural space provided by the nature of our sensor system, together with the design of the sound environments, allow for an experience of performing in real-time [37]–[39]. Although the dimensionality of the gestural space is theoretically unlimited, the capability of humans to navigate this space in real-time is not [40]. Doubtlessly, this depends on the individual skills of the human agents and the time they have already spent within the musical ecosystem. The current interaction design of Sentire aims to provide a gestural space accessible to novices. Future versions of the system should include options to challenge more trained users and may even automatically change the affordances based on how the interactants navigate the gestural space.

3.3 Intensifying the Intimate and Personal Space

The intimate (less than 0.5m) and personal (0.5m-1.2m) space, as classified by anthropologist Edward Hall describe culturally dependent zones of interpersonal distance influencing how people interact [41]. We conform with [42] that Hall’s proxemics studies should be considered in Interaction Design. Furthermore, with (c-e), we apply the concept of digital proxemics [43], designing a sonic-aesthetic experience that aims to intensify and foster interaction in the intimate and personal space [1], [44]. Intensifying the experience does not necessarily mean using a higher pitch or louder volume in close range. For example, We can also achieve this by making the frequency distribution more harmonic, changing the amount and speed of automatic modulations or by choosing a specific tonal mode [44].

3.4 Promoting Prosociality

Sociality and social interaction are crucial aspects of human health. In line with [45], we believe that musical sound can be a valuable tool to facilitate prosocial behaviours [46], [47]. Studies show that synchronisation/entrainment related to movement and musical structures strengthens prosocial behaviour through empathy and affiliation [48], [49]. We think that sonifying specific interaction behaviours can help to further promote prosociality. Our approach seeks to detect specific movement patterns from the sensor input with the help of deep learning and add the resulting higher-level input cues to the gestural space (see figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of Sentire with integrated gesture recognition.

4. DATA AND MODEL DESCRIPTION

Our data set for gesture classification consists of recorded proximity sensor data from 40 sessions of dyadic interactions and annotations of gestures gathered from structured observation (SO). The process of collecting data from SO is cumbersome, and therefore we designed our data processing, training and inference pipelines to comply with a small corpus.

4.1 Data collection

During data collection, we needed to synchronise the sensor data recording with the video recordings used for labelling. Since no simple tool existed that could record multiple high-resolution camera streams and be synchronised via the network, we developed a python based application which we can connect to our software via *Open Sound Control* (OSC). We additionally use this tool to play back recorded interactions, simulating auditory feedback with SuperCollider during sonic interaction design. The software is open source and available as a python package [50].

Sentire’s sensor system builds on capacitive coupling, and amplitude measurements through an audio codec [44]. Therefore, the raw sensor data is processed in the audio domain using the SuperCollider programming language (see figure 1). For practical reasons, our software stores the calculated proximity signal in the *Waveform Audio File*

Format (WAV). Yet, the input used for sonification and training does not encode an actual audio signal but movement data. In contrast to audio data, the proximity signal is unipolar (0–1, maximum distance–touch) and mainly has low-frequency content ($f < 1\text{Hz}$). The sensor data’s narrow bandwidth contributes significantly to our system’s minimal design. It decreases the end-to-end training/inference times, where it takes only a few minutes to train, and inference ranges between 1 to 2 seconds, depending on the sample length.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. 20 seconds of recorded proximity data (a) and corresponding annotations in ELAN (b) gathered through structured observation (SO).

Figure 3 shows an excerpt (20 seconds) of proximity data and the corresponding annotations made within the *ELAN* software using three high-resolution video recordings of the interaction from different angles. The available annotations result from a coding scheme developed within the project to investigate the relationship between sound and sociality [1].

4.2 Data Processing

We aimed to design a compact and rich training dataset without significant loss of proximity information and annotated observations. To that end, we applied the following data pre-processing steps:

Downsampling We downsampled the proximity sensor data by a factor of 1,000 from 48kHz to 48Hz. Though we process the initial sensor data in the audio domain, the slow nature of interactive movements limits the frequency content of the sensor signal. An comparison of the proximity signal before and after the downsampling showed that the reduced bandwidth does not change the signal characteristics. The lower sampling rate allowed us to design more compact and less resource-demanding models, which we ideally can use in a real-time prediction setting.

Speed vector calculation and feature extraction For each proximity sensor data sample, we computed the speed vector to be used as an additional input to the model. The speed vector is calculated through the first derivative of the proximity data, i.e. the amount of change in proximity over time. In addition, we extracted nine features at frame levels. For each frame, we computed the following features: IQR, centroid, signal magnitude area, energy and root-mean-square energy, mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum and median absolute deviation values. We computed these nine features for the proximity signal and the speed vector, resulting in an additional 18-dimensional vector.

Input data batching Each batch has a size of 512 frames and contains data from a distinct session during training. We padded the start of each batch with a null vector to signal the start of the respective session. We also padded the end of each batch with null vectors to signal the end, where the number of null frames added up to 512 frames to ensure that each batch mapped to a particular session. Sessions with longer durations were split into multiple batches, where the padding at the end was applied only to the last batch.

Data augmentation During training, we simultaneously used batches of sessions constructed with different hop sizes, i.e. how much we advanced the time among consecutive frames. Each batch of data was introduced four times with hop sizes of 1.0, 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25. Smaller hop sizes generate more training samples. Therefore, we set the sample weight inversely proportional to the hop size. In addition to using different hop sizes, we also generated training batches using four different frame sizes of 1, 2, 3, and 4 seconds, whereby a frame of 1 second corresponds to 48 samples. We used combinations of these two sets of parameters to obtain 16 training rounds, assuming that the model can more reliably capture time dependencies at different granularities within a sequence.

4.3 Label Set Description

Out of all the annotated labels, we focused on those that might affect the proximity signal and therefore pruned labels describing no motion (e.g. ‘rest position’, ‘gaze’). Table 1 provides an overview of the labels used for training. We use a total of eight labels, which are under two top-tier gesture classes, namely *whole body* and *arm* movements. A *tier* is a category for annotations that share the same set of characteristics. According to this definition, the *whole body* tier, for example, categorises all annotations for interactions where the whole body is involved. All the labels were annotated individually for the two participants, except the *whole body:copy* label. This label is positive only in cases where both participants performed a similar bodily gesture and corresponds to imitation.

We could map the timeline of annotated gestures to each second of processed data since the gestures were annotated

Tier	Label
<i>whole body</i>	backward step/s
	lateral step/s
	forward step/s
	full circle
	turning steps
<i>arms</i>	copy (imitation)
	one towards
	both towards

Table 1. Labels used for training and testing the models.

with timestamps in milliseconds granularity, signalling the start and end of each gesture.

4.4 Model Description

We trained separate models for the aforementioned two top tiers (see Figure 4). Each model uses two convolu-

Figure 4. CNN model architecture. There are two identical CNNs, each consisting of four blocks with residual connections. The proximity and speed vector inputs are passed through the two CNNs separately. For simplicity, only one of the CNNs is plotted, where the speed input’s stack is represented by a dashed arrow.

tional neural networks (CNNs) with residual connections that process sequences of proximity signals and their speed vector separately. The aforementioned frame-level features are processed by a separate dense layer, whose output is concatenated to the outputs of the two CNNs. We use a sigmoid objective to align these three outputs, and a weighted binary cross-entropy loss, suited for the multi-label classification task. Each label within the tiers is annotated for the two participants separately. However, at training time, we merged labels from both participants into sequences of multi-label target outputs. At inference time, the two models take as input the same input sensor and feature data to predict the respective labels within the tier. It would also

be possible to train each tier-level model for the participants separately, but we think this would limit our capability to use the system in a setting with multiple participants.

The two tier-level models use four dilated convolutional blocks, each of which is constructed from residual stacks with weight normalisation. These convolutional blocks are constructed separately for the downsampled sensor and speed vectors. The outputs of the two blocks are concatenated and passed to the final multi-headed output layer with two heads, one for each participant.

5. MODEL EVALUATION

Out of the 40 recorded sessions, we used fixed sets of 30, 4 and 6 sessions for training, validation and evaluation of our models, respectively. We scored each model in the ensemble separately and aggregated the predictions. To compare performances across the labels, we fixed a precision level of 0.8 for each label and computed the f1-score at that precision level.

Figure 5. Average f1-scores and standard deviation per label for the ResNet-CNN model (blue) and the logistic regression baseline (red).

Figure 5 shows the resulting metrics, including a comparison with a baseline for each label based on a logistic regression model whose binary outcome is whether the gesture took place or not. We calculated scores by averaging the outcomes for each session. The resulting metrics vary significantly for each label. We observed considerable uplift for three gestures: *arms:one towards* (f1:0.11/0.65), *arms:both towards* (f1:0.27/0.79) and *whole body:copy* (f1:0.21/0.51). Gestures that are expected to produce a distinctive sensor signal perform better (e.g. arms movements involving one or both arms). In contrast, gestures that intuitively might produce sensor signals without a consistent pattern (e.g. *backward* and *turning steps*, *full circle*) are poorly detected. Gestures involving steps performed better than the baseline, though not with such a significant uplift than gestures including arm movements.

As a proof of concept, we wanted to quantify and compare the level of misclassifications across and within tiers. Intuitively, if the model makes more mistakes within top tiers (e.g. mislabeling *one towards* with *both towards*), this would still show that the training did not fail significantly and so would help us conclude that there is space for improvement. To that end, we created inter-tier predictors by aggregating the predicted and true labels into their top tiers, where the occurrence of any of the labels within a tier is treated as a positive label, and computed *Cohen’s Kappa Coefficient* [51] κ to empirically test the relationship between inter- and intra-tier predictions. We obtain κ for the intra-tier setting by aggregating the performance of the models for individual classes into a single average κ metric. Kappa Coefficient is defined in Eq. (1) as follows:

$$\kappa = \frac{Pr_a - Pr_e}{1 - Pr_e} \quad (1)$$

where Pr_a is the relative observed agreement between classification and test data, and Pr_e is the hypothetical probability of chance agreement, where the observed data are used to calculate probabilities of each rater to choose a label at random. In this case, $\kappa = 1$ if the raters are in complete agreement, and $\kappa \leq 0$ if they are in agreement only to the extent of what is expected by chance (as defined by Pr_e). We chose Kappa coefficient since it captures a combination of precision and recall similar to the f1-score value, but includes the comparison to the baseline of a random classifier in its calculation. Using the f1-score for evaluating a random classifier would instead be dependent on the distribution of the classes, whereas Kappa Coefficient is independent of class size and thus is resilient to biases introduced by differing class sizes.

Tier	Label	κ
<i>whole body</i>	inter-tier	0.58
	intra-tier	0.13
<i>arms</i>	inter-tier	0.41
	intra-tier	0.14

Table 2. Kappa coefficients for inter- and intra-tier predictions.

Table 2 provides the intra- and inter-tier coefficients. There are significantly higher levels of agreement for the inter-tier setting for both tiers. Therefore we can safely hypothesise that prediction errors are related more to specific labels, and less to the question of the predictability of gestures at large.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The described approach demonstrates the possibility of classifying interactive gestures from one-dimensional proximity data. Despite the ultra-low dimensionality of our sensor signal and a relatively small data set derived from structured observation, we can predict interactive behaviours that intuitively affect the proximity signal. Especially gestures with arm movements perform significantly better than a linear regression baseline. The approach is not restricted

to proximity data and gestural input. In the context of sonification, the method can be abstracted to classifying time-based events in one-dimensional data streams. Granted that enough labelled data exist, the model architecture could be the ground for event-based sonification for a broad range of health and environmental data. Its real-time feasibility could be especially relevant for process monitoring tasks that require immediate sound feedback. Future work should include cross validation and investigate the effect of a larger corpus and more diverse augmentation/noising techniques. At the time of writing, the presented work serves as a proof of concept, and an actual implementation for real-time sonification remains. We think that adding interactive gestures to the gestural space of our interactive system could help to promote prosociality. Testing this hypothesis should be the subject of subsequent studies. Finally, we encourage the discourse on whether the effort spent to follow the deep learning trend is justified. A straightforward approach based on raw sensor input and higher-level statistic features, combined with well-designed parameter mappings, could achieve similar results while leaving more time to focus on the artistic facets of the interdisciplinary project.

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